

ISSN (p): 3030-3362

№ 2(24)

27.02.2025

IF 2024
11.7

R

TADQIQ VA TATBIQ

Research and implementation

scientific-methodical journal

S C I E N C E S

Exact, Natural, Political, Social, Economic, Technical, Medical, Pedagogical

INTERNATIONAL
STANDARD
SERIAL
NUMBER
INTERNATIONAL CENTRE

CERTIFICATE
№ 078777

 ral-journal.uz

 [@ferteach_uz](https://twitter.com/ferteach_uz)

Editor in Chief:

F.M.Mukhtarov
PhD, associate prof

Executive editor

S.I.Zokirov
PhD, associate prof

Languages:

Uzbek, Russian, English and
Karakalpak

Registered in the Agency of
Information and Mass
Communications under the
Administration of the
President of the Republic of
Uzbekistan on May 3, 2023
under number 078777.

[IF-2024: 11.7](#)

 [@feritech_uz](https://t.me/feritech_uz)

 +99893-343-13-14

 <https://rai-journal.uz>

Editorial Board:

B.R.Ismailov – Dr. Tech. Sc., Prof., M.Avezov South Kaz. Univ., Shymkent, Kazakhstan
I.Bjorn – Ph.D., Imeritus, Technical University of Denmark, Copenhagen, Denmark
A.Rasulov – Dr. Phys.-Math. Sc., Prof., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
L.K.Mamadaliyeva – Dr. Tech. Sc. (DSc), Prof., FerPI, Fergana, Uzbekistan
M.E.Yunusaliyev – Dr. Tech. Sc. (DSc), Prof., FerPI, Fergana, Uzbekistan
X.B.Ismailov – Can. Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., M.Avezov South Kaz. Univ., Shymkent, Kazakhstan
J.T.Moldaliyev – Can. Bio. Sc., Assoc. Prof., OshSU, Osh, Kyrgyzstan
O.S.Nazarmatov – DSc in Econ., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
G.K.Obidova – DSc in Ped., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
T.M.Abdullayev – Ph.D. in Tech. Sc., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
N.I.Ibrokhimov – Ph.D. in Phys.-Math., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
A.R.Nurmatov – Ph.D. in History, NamSU, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
T.Yu.Bakirov – PhD in Ped. Sc., FarSU, Fergana, Uzbekistan
D.F.Tukhtasinov – Ph.D. in Ped. Sc., TUIT Fergana branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
S.B.Atajonova – Ph.D in Ped. Sc., AndMI, Andijan Uzbekistan
Sh.A.Umarov – Ph.D. in Phys.-Math. Sc., TUIT Fergana branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
I.A.Rustamov – Ph.D. in Phil. Sc., TUIT Fergana branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
B.Kh.Tolipov – Ph.D. in Phil. Sc., TUIT Fergana branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
O.Kh.Otakulov – Can. Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., TUIT Fergana branch, Uzbekistan
O.S.Raimjonova – Ph.D in Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., TUIT Fergana branch, Uzbekistan
R.A.Nuridinova – Ph.D in Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., TUIT Fergana branch, Uzbekistan
M.I.Ismoilov – Ph.D in Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., TUIT Fergana branch, Uzbekistan
I.T.Tojiboyev – Can. Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., Fergana State University, Uzbekistan
Sh.J.Kholmatov – Ph.D., TUIT Fergana branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
Z.N.Khatamova – Ph.D. in Tech. Sc., TUIT Fergana branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
Q.Kh. Akhunov – Can. Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., Fergana Polytechnic Institute, Uzbekistan
M.Kh. Okhunov – Can. Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., Fergana Polytechnic Institute, Uzbekistan
A.Q. Khomidov – Can. Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., Fergana Polytechnic Institute, Uzbekistan
Sh.Sh. Akramov – PhD, TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
A.A. Salimov – PhD in Econ., Fergana Polytechnic Institute, Uzbekistan
Z.G'. Ubaydullayev – Can. Econ., TUIT Qarchi Branch, Qarchi, Uzbekistan
S.S. Ibragimov – Ph.D in Tech. Sc., AndMI, Andijan Uzbekistan
Sh.J. Kholmatov – Ph.D. in Phil., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
G.D. Kuchkarova – Ph.D. in Phil., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
I.R.Teshabayeva – Ph.D. in Tech. Sc., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
A.L.Meliqzuyev – Ph.D. in Phil. Sc., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
O.U.Kholmatova – Ph.D. in Phil. Sc., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
N.N.Radjabov – Ph.D. in Phil. Sc., Assoc. Prof., Oriental University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan
Sh.A.Yuldashov – Ph.D. in Tech. Sc., Fergana State University, Fergana, Uzbekistan
A.A.Yuldashev – Ph.D. in Tech. Sc., Fergana State University, Fergana, Uzbekistan
M.Israilov – Can. Tech. Sc., Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan Academy of Forces
N.S.Abdullaeva – PhD in Ped. Sc., NamDU, Namangan, Uzbekistan
A.G.Turgunboeva – PhD in Ped. Sc., NamDPI, Namangan, Uzbekistan
M.A.Abdullaeva – Prof., NamDU, Namangan, Uzbekistan
I.O.Ergashev – PhD in Econ., Fiscal Institute, Tashkent, Uzbekistan
N.T.Mamatxanova – PhD in Ped. Sc., NamDPI, Namangan, Uzbekistan
U.Yu.Akhundzhanov – PhD in Tech. Sc., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
O.M.Ergashev – PhD in Tech. Sc., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
N.R.Khallieva – PhD in Econ., Bukhara MTI, Bukhara, Uzbekistan
F.K.Achilova – Can. Econ. Sc., TUIT Qarchi Branch, Qarchi, Uzbekistan
A.K.Samyayev – PhD in Geog., Sam. Reg. Ped. Skills Center, Samarkand, Uzbekistan
J.S.Abdullayev – Can. Phys.-Math. Sc., Assoc. Prof., TUIT Fergana branch, Uzbekistan
N.D.Botirova – PhD in Ped, TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan

Bosh muharrir:

F.M.Mukhtarov
PhD, dotsent

Ijrochi muharrir:

S.I.Zokirov
PhD, dotsent

Nashr tillari:

O'zbek, Rus, Inzliz va
Qoraqalpoq

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Prezidenti Administratsiyasi
huzuridagi Axborot va
ommaviy
kommunikatsiyalar agentligi
tomonidan 2023-yil 3-
mayda 078777 raqami bilan
ro'yxatga olingan..

IF-2024: 11.7

 [@feriteach_uz](https://t.me/feriteach_uz)
 +99893-343-13-14
 <https://rai-journal.uz>

Editorial Board:

B.R.Ismailov – t.f.d., prof. M.Avezov Jan. Qoz. Univ-ti., Chimkent, Qozog'iston
I.Byorno - Ph.D., Imeritus, Daniya Texnika Universiteti, Kopengagen, Daniya
A.Rasulov – f.-m.f.d., prof.TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
L.K.Mamadaliyeva – t.f.d. (DSc), prof. FarPI, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
M.E.Yunusaliyev – t.f.d. (DSc), prof. FarPI, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
X.B.Ismailov- t.f.n., dot., M.Avezov Jan. Qoz. Univ-ti., Chimkent, Qozog'iston
J.T.Moldaliyev - bio. f. n., dotsent. OshDU, Osh, Qirg'iziston
O.S.Nazarmatov - iqt.f.d. DSc, TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
G.K.Obidova - ped.f.d. DSc, TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
T.M.Abdullayev – t.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
N.I.Ibrokhimov – f.-m.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
A.R.Nurmatov – tarix f.b. Ph.D., NamDU, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
T.Yu.Bakirov - ped. f.b. PhD, FarDU, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
D.F.To'xtasinov - ped.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
S.B.Atajonova - ped.f.b. Ph.D, AndMI, Andijon O'zbekiston
Sh.A.Umarov - f.-m.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
I.A.Rustamov - fal.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
B.X.Tolipov - f.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
O.X.Otaqulov – t.f.n., dotsent. TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston
O.S.Raimjonova – t.f.b. Ph.D, dotsent, TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston
R.A.Nurdinova – t.f.b. Ph.D, dotsent, TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston
M.I.Ismoilov – t.f.b. Ph.D, dotsent, TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston
I.T.Tojiboyev – t.f.n., dotsent, Farg'ona davlat universiteti, O'zbekiston
Sh.J.Kholmatov - i.i.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
Z.N.Khatamova - t.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
Q.X. Axunov - t.f.n., dotsent, Farg'ona politexnika instituti, O'zbekiston
M.X. Oxunov - t.f.n., dotsent, Farg'ona politexnika instituti, O'zbekiston
A.Q.Xomidov - t.f.n., dotsent, Farg'ona politexnika instituti, O'zbekiston
Sh.Sh.Akramov – q.x.f.b. PhD, TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
A.A.Salimov - iqt.f.b. PhD, Farg'ona politexnika instituti, O'zbekiston
Z.G'.Ubaydullayev - iqt.f.n., TATU Qarchi filiali, Qarchi, O'zbekiston
S.S.Ibragimov - t.f.b. Ph.D, AndMI, Andijon O'zbekiston
Sh.J.Xolmatov- fal.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
G.D.Kuchkarova- fal.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
I.R.Teshabayeva - t.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
A.L.Meliquziyev- fil.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
O.U.Xolmatova- fil.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
N.N.Radjabov- fil.f.b. Ph.D., dotsent, Oriental University, Toshkent, O'zbekiston
Sh.A.Yuldashov - t.f.b. Ph.D., Farg'ona davlat universiteti, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
A.A.Yuldashev - t.f.b. Ph.D., Farg'ona davlat universiteti, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
M.Israilov - t.f.n., O'zbekiston Respublikasi Qurolli Kuchlar Akademiyasi
N.S.Abdullayeva - p.f.b. PhD, NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston
A.G.Turg'unboyeva - p.f.b. PhD, NamDPI, Namangan, O'zbekiston
M.A.Abdullayeva - professor, NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston
I.O.Ergashev – iqt.f.b. PhD, Fiskal instituti, Toshkent, O'zbekiston
N.T.Mamatxanova - p.f.b. PhD, NamDPI, Namangan, O'zbekiston
U.Yu.Axundjanov - t.f.b. PhD, TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
O.M.Ergashev - t.f.b. PhD, TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
N.R.Xallieva - iqt.f.b. PhD, Buxoro MTI, Buxoro, O'zbekiston
F.K.Achilova - iqt.f.n., TATU Qarchi filiali, Qarchi, O'zbekiston
A.K.Samyayev - g.f.b. PhD, Sam. vil. ped. mah. mar, Samarqand, O'zbekiston
J.S.Abdullayev - f.-m.f.n., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
N.D.Botirova – ped.f.b. PhD, TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston

Rodiola o'simligining dorivor xususiyatlari va zamonaviy farmakalogiyada qo'llanilishi

¹Atabekova Mashxura Usmanovna, ²Abdug'aniyeva Naziraxon Dilmurodjon qizi

¹ *Kokand university Andijon filiali, assistent*

² *Kokand university Andijon filiali, talaba*

Copyright: © 2025 by the author.

Licensee: This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada Rhodiola o'simligining dorivor xususiyatalari va uning zamonaviy farmakalogiyada tutgan o'rnini tadqiq qilishga bag'ishlangan. Tadqiqotda o'simlikning asosiy biokimyoviy tarkibi, jumladan, flavonoidlar, efir moylari va organik kislatalar keltirilgan. Rhodiola adaptogen sifatida stress, charchoq, hamda atrof - muhitning salbiy ta'sirlariga qarshi kurashda muhim vosita sifatida ko'rib chiqiladi. Maqolada Rhodiola ildizining terepevtik xususiyatlari, xalq tabobatida qo'llanilish tarixi va zamonaviy ilmiy tadqiqotlar natijalari tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, ushbu o'simlik asosida ishlab chiqariladigan farmasevtik vositalar va ular tibbiyotda qo'llanishining istiqbollari muhokama qilinadi. Rhodiola o'simligining ahamiyatini o'rganish nafaqat tabiat resuslarini oqilona boshqarish, balki yangi dori vositalarini yaratishda ham muhim ro'l o'ynaydi. Mazkur ish adaptogen o'simliklarning stressga qarshi tabiiy yechim sifatidagi ahamiyatini yanada chuqur o'rganishga qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Rodiola, dorivor o'simlik, farmakalogiya, adaptogen, stress, trapevtik xususiyatlar, biokimyoviy tarkib, dorilar, xalq taboati.

Received: 16 Feb. 2025

Accepted: 17 Feb. 2025

Published: 18 Feb 2025

Kirish: Rhodiola o'simligi qadimdan xalq tabobatida foydalanilgan dorivor o'simlik hisoblanadi. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, rhodiola asosan, tog'li hududlarda o'sib, biologik faol moddalar bilan boy tarkibga ega. Ushbu o'simlikning ildizi va yer ustki qismlari an'anaviy tibbiyotda asab tizimi mustahkamlash, charchoqni kamaytirish va organizmning umumiy tonusini oshirish uchun ishlatilgan. Rhodiola ildizi flavonoidlar, organik kislatalar va antioksidantlar kabi moddalarga boy bo'lib, bu uning stress va boshqa salbiy omillarga qarshi kurashuvchi adaptogen sifatida keng qo'llanilishiga asos bo'ladi. Hozirgi zamonaviy farmakalogiyada rhodiola asosida ishlab chiqilgan preparatlar stressga qarshi vosita sifatida qo'llanilmoqda. Shuningdek, ilmiy tadqiqotlar davomida uning immunitetni oshiruvchi, asab tizimi tinchlantiruvchi va kognitiv funksialarni yaxshilovchi hususiyatlari aniqlangan.

Asosiy qism : Rhodiola o’simligining o’simligining biokimyoviy tarkibi:

Rhodiola o’simligi biologic faol moddalar bilan boy bo’lib, uning dorivor xususiyatlari ushbu moddalar ta’siriga asoslangan. O’simlikning ildizi va yer usti qismlarida flamonoidlar, glikozidlar, efir moylari, taninlar, organic kislatalar va salidrozd kabi moddalarning mavjudligi aniqlangan. Ayniqsa , salidrozd va rozavin birikmalari rhodiola ildizining asosiy faol komponentlari bo’lib, ular stressga qarshi tasir ko’rsatishda muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Adaptogen sifatidagi ahamiyati: Rhodiola adoptogen o’simlik sifatida organizmning stressga moslashish qobilyatini oshiradi. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko’rsatadiki, rhodiola preparadlari asab tizimini mustahkamlash, charchoqni kamaytirish va diqqatni oshirishda foydali. U shuningdek kortizol garmonining sekretiyyasini kamaytirib, stressning organizmga salbiy tasirani kamaytiradi.

	<p>Kognitiv funksiyalarni yaxshilash: Xotira va diqqatni kuchaytiruvchi ta'sir ko'rsatadi.</p>		
		<p>Energiya va chidamlilikni oshirish:Organizmning jismoniy va ruhiy kuchini tiklashda yordam beradi.</p>	

Farmakologik qo’llanilishi: Hozirgi zamonaviy farmasevtikada Rhodiola asosida turli preparatlar ishlab chiqarilmoqda . Ular asosan, stressga qarshi , charchoqni kamaytiruvchi hamda depressiyaga qarshi vosita sifatida ishlatiladi. Rhodiola preparatlari xavfsizligi va kam nojo’ya ta’siri tufayli keng qo’llanilmoqda.

Rhadiola o’simligining kimyoviy tarkibi

TARKIBIY GURUH	ASOSIY BIRIKMALARI	FUNKSIYASI
Fenilpropanoidlar	Salidrozd, rozavin, rozarin, rozin	Stressga chidamlilikni oshiradi, antioksidant xususiyatiga ega
Feniletanol hosilalari	Tirozol, salidrozd	Nerv tizimi mustahkamlaydi,antioksidant ta’sir ko’rsatadi
Flavonoidlar	Kaempferol, kuarsetin, rodionin	Yurak-qon tomir tizimini himoyalsh
Monoterpenlar va Triterpenlar	Beta-sitosterol	Imunitetni mustahkamlash, yallig’lanishga qarshi

Organik kislotalar	Gallic kislota, xlorogen kislota, kumarin kislotalari	Antioksidant, detoksifikatsiya jarayoni qo'llab-quvvatlash
Polisakkaridlar	Murakkab uglevodlar	Immunitetni mustahkamlash
Aminokislotalar	L- prolin, L-tirozin	Metabolizmni yaxshilash, stressni kamaytirish

Xalq tabobatida qollanilishi: Rhodiola o'simligi ko'p asrlar davomida xalq tabobatida qo'llanilib kelgan. Masalan: Sibir va Markaziy Osiyo axolisi uni charchoq va sovuqdan himoya qilishda ishlatgan. Shuningdek, Rhodiola sharbatlari va qaynatmalari asab tizimini tinchlantirishda ham foydali hisoblangan.

Xulosa: Rhodiola (**oltin ildiz**) o'simligi qadimdan xalq tabobatida dorivor xususiyatlari bilan mashhur bo'lgan. Uning tarkibida salidrozyd, rozavin, rosarin kabi biologik faol moddalar mavjud bo'lib, ular organizmga ko'plab ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

Zamonaviy farmakologiyada Rhodiola o'simligining quyidagi jihatlari keng o'rganilib, qo'llanilmoqda: **Stressga qarshi ta'siri:** Adaptogen xususiyatga ega bo'lib, organizmning stressga moslashuvchanligini oshiradi, nerv tizimini tinchlantiradi va charchoqni kamaytiradi. **Immunitetni mustahkamlash:** Antioksidant ta'siri sababli erkin radikallarga qarshi kurashadi, hujayralarni oksidlanish jarayonidan himoya qiladi.

Yallig'lanishga qarshi ta'siri: Organizmning yallig'lanish jarayonlarini kamaytiradi va regeneratsiyani tezlashtiradi.

Jismoniy va aqliy salohiyatni oshirish: Charchoqni bartaraf etib, diqqat va konsentratsiyani yaxshilashga yordam beradi. Shu sababli sportchilar va aqliy faoliyat bilan shug'ullanuvchilar orasida ommalashgan.

Kardiohimoya ta'siri: Yurak qon-tomir tizimini qo'llab-quvvatlaydi, qon aylanishini yaxshilaydi va qon bosimini me'yorda ushlab turishga yordam beradi.

Rhodiola asosida yaratilgan preparatlar va oziq-ovqat qo'shimchalari depressiya, uyqu buzilishi, surunkali charchoq sindromi, past qon bosimi, diabet kabi holatlarda muvaffaqiyatli qo'llanilmoqda. Zamonaviy ilmiy tadqiqotlar uning tarkibiy qismlarining potentsial onkologik kasalliklarga qarshi xususiyatlarini ham o'rganmoqda. Shu bilan birga, Rhodiola o'simligini qo'llash individual yondashuvni talab qiladi, chunki uni noto'g'ri ishlatish nojo'ya ta'sirlarga olib kelishi mumkin. Mazkur o'simlikning tabiiy va xavfsiz alternativ vosita sifatida qadri tobora ortib bormoqda, bu esa uni farmakologiya va sog'lomlashtirish sohasida qo'llash imkoniyatlarini kengaytirmoqda.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Panossian, A., & Wagner, H. "Adaptogens in Stress Management: Pharmacological and Clinical Perspectives"
2. Asqarov, I., & Razzakov, N. (2022). Зирк меваси таркибидаги табиий бирикмаларнинг иммуностимуляторлик хоссалари. *Farg'ona davlat universiteti*, (1), 13-13.
3. Kucinskaite, A., Briedis, V., & Savickas, A. "Pharmacological and Therapeutic Effects of *Rhodiola Rosea* L." (*Journal of Medicinal Plants Research*)
4. Khanum, F., Bawa, A. S., & Singh, B. "Rhodiola Rosea: A Versatile Adaptogen" (*Comprehensive Reviews in Food Science and Food Safety*)
5. Winston, D., & Maimes, S. "Adaptogens: Herbs for Strength, Stamina, and Stress Relief"
6. Herbal Gram "Rhodiola Rosea: A Detailed Review of Clinical and Pharmacological Data" (*American Botanical Council*)
7. Аскарлов, И. Р., & Раззаков, Н. А. (2023). Ginkgo bilobaning flavonoid tarkibi. *Журнал химии товаров и народной медицины*, 2(3), 166-173.

Scientific-methodical journal “Research and implementation”

Address:

150100, Fergana region, Fergana, Solim street, 23/4, apt. 26

E-mail:

chief_editor@rai-journal.uz

Our website:

<https://rai-journal.uz/>

The Scientific-methodical journal “Research and implementation” was founded by LLC Fer-Teach and supported by the Fergana branch of the Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khorezmi. This journal was registered by the Agency of Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on May 3, 2023 (No 078777).

ISSN 3030-3362.

"Research and implementation" is a specialized journal in the field of technology and covers all major areas of research and development in various fields of technical sciences: physics, mathematics, information technology. The journal also publishes scientific articles on linguistics, teaching methods and the history of the development of technical sciences.

Languages: Uzbek, Russian, English, Karakalpak

ВНИМАНИЕ!

При использовании материалов журнала необходимо указывать источник
Авторы статей несут ответственность за содержание статей и за сам факт их
публикации.

Редакция не всегда разделяет мнения авторов и не несет ответственности за
недостоверность публикуемых данных.

Редакция журнала не несет никакой ответственности перед авторами и/или
третьими лицами и организациями за возможный ущерб, вызванный
публикацией статьи.

ATTENTION!

When using journal materials, you must indicate the source.

The authors of the articles are responsible for the content of the articles and for the
very fact of their publication.

The editors do not always share the opinions of the authors and are not responsible for
the unreliability of the published data.

The editorial board of the journal does not bear any responsibility to the authors and /
or third parties and organizations for possible damage caused by the publication of the
article

DIQQAT!

Jurnal materiallaridan foydalanganda manbani ko'rsatish kerak.

Maqola mualliflari maqolalar mazmuni va ularning nashr etilishi fakti uchun
javobgardirlar.

Har doim ham mualliflarning fikrlari tahririyat nuqtai nazarini ifodalamaydi va nashr
etilgan ma'lumotlarning haqiqiyliги uchun javobgar emas.

Jurnal tahririyati mualliflar va/yoki uchinchi shaxslar va tashkilotlarga maqolaning
e'lon qilinishi natijasida yetkazilishi mumkin bo'lgan zarar uchun javobgar emas.